

MEET NATALIA

Natalia Oliveros Gomez represented **Colombia** at the IPT 2019 and IPT 2020

Looking back, what first motivated you to join the International Physicists' Tournament?

Initially, I was motivated by the curiosity of "this is what a physicist really does." Try to answer open questions without a specific answer from all possible means (theory, experiments, and simulations).

And I was barely halfway through my undergraduate studies, so it was quite challenging. And for me, another important reason was that I was going to do it with friends, so I thought it would also unite us even more.

Which IPT problem, debate, or experience left the strongest impression on you – and why?

Some problems did, I'm going to take 2: the radio potato in 2019... This problem also led us to learn a lot about electronic engineering. We use simulators, but, in addition, and what was most important, I learned about the different types of potatoes we have in South America and how they can have different properties, even being "the same". We managed to do it, we took our prototype to Switzerland, and we did well with that problem. Also, the jumping beans problem in 2020 was so fun. How can we extract the science of a "simple" game? And we do the theory of the movements, the experiments, record and change all the possible parameters, and simulate our theory and fit it to the trajectories of the beans. It was amazing!

How did participating in the IPT shape your approach to research, teamwork, or communication in your later studies or career?

It helped me a lot! The IPT was my first approach to research, and although I now work in Astrophysics, the processes of carrying out a project are similar. I learned to be very organized and that it is important to trust the work of others in the group, so the load is lightened, and it can even be part of the strategy to enhance each person's best abilities.

Where has your journey taken you since your IPT days academically?

I finished my physics degree in Colombia at the Universidad Industrial de Santander and went to Mexico to pursue a Master of Science in Astrophysics at the University of Guanajuato. And I'm currently doing my PhD also in Physics and Astronomy at Johns Hopkins University in the USA. I study the atmospheric variability of brown dwarfs and exoplanets. At the same time, I am a part of many science communication projects, because for me it is an essential part of being a scientist, including a profile on IG where I do outreach mainly in Spanish [@arrecifecosmico](#), talking about astronomy news, my life as a PhD student, my immigration journey, and more. In addition, I'm part of the RECA organization (Network of Colombian Students in Astronomy), where I help bring astronomy to rural and urban schools throughout my country, Colombia, by providing real-life examples of local astronomers and opportunities to do science, regardless of the conditions where we grow up.

What's one skill or lesson from the IPT that you still find yourself using today?

The importance of planning well how you want to develop a project, assigning tasks and deadlines so they are met. Know how to show most of the development of a problem in a limited time, and finally know how to ask questions about other people's solutions to start conversations and interesting opportunities with other possible collaborators.